

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The use of comic strips to improve the student's reading comprehension of narrative text (An Action Research at the Students of English for Teens Program in Language Learning Center)

Fitrianita Febrina Ali *, Moon Hidayati Otoluwa and Jolanda Hulda Debora Pilongo

Universitas Negeri Gorontalo, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 19(02), 616–626

Publication history: Received on 14 June 2023; revised on 26 July 2023; accepted on 28 July 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.19.2.1482>

Abstract

This research presented the findings of a study aiming to investigate whether comic strips can help students to improve their reading comprehension skills in English. This research was conducted at the English for Teens Program in Language Learning Center with 21 students as the participants. The text in focus was narrative. This research used action research using Kemmis and Taggart's design, which consists of four steps: planning, action, observation, and reflection. The data were collected from observation and tests. The data observation has obtained the teacher and students' teaching and learning reading comprehension activities. Nevertheless, test results were collected from student tests in each cycle. It illustrates that despite some parts that need improvement, using comic strips can improve students' reading comprehension skills in narrative text. The portraits of students' progress in reading comprehension of the narrative text of some cycles show that in the first cycle, only 19% of students could reach the Value of 80 or more as the success criteria. In the second cycle, 100% of students successfully passed the test. Observation data shows that the students were encouraged to learn reading comprehension of narrative text using comic strips in group or individual works. Based on the study results, that comic strip is recommended to implement in other genres, especially narrative text or other language skills.

Keywords: Reading; Comprehension; Narrative text; Comic strip

1. Introduction

Teaching media is the equipment used in the teaching and learning process to achieve learning goals and make learning more enjoyable. According to Sudjana and Rivai in Rokhayani et al. (2014), there are several things to highlight in teaching media. First, the teacher must clearly understand what teaching media is, the types of teaching media, how to use teaching media, and what are the advantages of teaching media. The teacher must also follow up on using the teaching and learning process. Second, the teachers must be capable of creating simple teaching media for the goals of teaching. Third, skills and knowledge are required to assess the effectiveness of media use in the teaching process.

According to Sudjana in Hasan et al. (2021), learning media has several benefits for the student's learning process. First, learning media attracts students' attention so that they can improve their learning motivation. Second, learning materials have a more precise meaning. Therefore, students can better understand them and enable them to achieve their learning objectives. Third, teaching methods be more varied, not solely verbal communication through the utterance of words by the teacher. Moreover, the students do not get bored, and the teachers do not run out of energy when teaching every lesson. Fourth, the students can do more learning activities because they listen to the teacher's description and other activities such as observing, demonstrating, and others.

*Corresponding author: Fitrianita Febrina Ali

Furthermore, teaching media is essential in teaching and learning because it can help the teacher deliver the material and help the students understand it more easily. The teacher can stimulate students' interest in the material by teaching media and building their curiosity. The students will be more curious about what they are going to learn. Thus, they will find out the essence of the material by themselves. Eventually, the teaching and learning process can achieve the goal by using the media.

In teaching reading, teachers must choose the selected media to make the students understand the material more accessible. Additionally, reading is one of many ways to improve the student's knowledge and thinking skills. One factor that influenced their reading abilities is their interest in reading. However, students still lack interest in reading books, mainly textbooks, because it seems difficult to understand and tedious—especially books full of plain text without pictures and colours. Students will usually be more interested in reading because of the visual interest in the text.

Based on the observation in the Language Learning Center, one of the courses institutions in Gorontalo Regency, the tutor mostly has a problem when teaching reading to the student, primarily narrative text. Because the researcher is one of the English tutors in the Language Learning Center, she observed the students' reading skill development. When the tutor teaches reading comprehension, primarily narrative text, the students always feel bored when reading the text and have a problem understanding the text. The lack of vocabulary and low interest in reading is the biggest problem that made the students struggle to read the text. They are also not familiar with the story of the text. Therefore, reading is a skill investigated in this research.

Based on this phenomenon, the teacher must find ways to increase the student's interest in reading. Because the teacher plays a significant role in the learning process, the teacher must be able to attract students' interest in learning by using media that can enchant the students' attention. The teacher can use comic strips as a learning medium to increase the student's motivation to read. Using comic strips, it hopes to attract students' attention and raise their interest in reading without feeling forced.

According to Smith in Aisy et al. (2019), comics can work as one of the significant bridges between literature and visual pleasure in today's era of entertainment, such as the internet, video games, and movies. Comics are essential in the classroom and can influence students' study habits. Many studies have demonstrated that comic books are an excellent resource for students with difficulty with reading on both skill and development factors.

In the curriculum applied in Indonesia, students are expected to master all types of text: descriptive text, procedure text, explanation text, recount text, narrative text, etc. The researcher chooses narrative text because a narrative is a text that tells a story to entertain the readers and has a moral lesson to our life. According to Anderson in Amrizal and Hamdani (2017), a narrative is a text that tells a story to entertain the readers. This research focused on Indonesian folklore, which has been translated into English. It aims to increase students' knowledge of Indonesian mythology. The researcher chooses narrative text and comic strips to attract students' attention in learning reading, the primary narrative text of Indonesian folklore.

The comic strip is suitable for applying to Language Learning Center because the students are interested in pictures, anime, and cartoons. Several researchers are investigating the strength of using comics in education. Yang in Yunus et al. (2012) stated that students have a natural capability about the picture, therefore the ability of comics to arrest and preserve learners' interest. Haugaard in Yunus et al. (2012) stated that children naturally have a fascination for comics. It would be great if the teacher could utilize the extraordinary influence of this comic to increase students' motivation to learn in class.

In discussing the case above, the researcher assumes that teaching English reading skills using comic strips is one of the teaching aids that make the opportunity to learn English more enjoyable. Because a comic combines pictures and sentences, it makes it easier for students to understand the content and context that the teacher has taught. Comic strips are hoped to motivate students to read and pay attention to the material, resulting in enjoyable English learning.

Therefore, the researcher investigated the use of comic strips by students in the Language Learning Center, especially in the English for Teens Program. The researchers used this media to solve problems that occur to students when they have difficulty understanding reading texts. However, in this study, the researcher is interested in conducting "The Use of Comic Strips to Improve the Students' Reading Comprehension of Narrative Text (An Action Research at the Students of English for Teens Program in Language Learning Center)." This research aims to know whether and how comic strips can improve the student's reading comprehension of the narrative in the Language Learning Center.

2. Methodology of research

This research was conducted among the English for Teens Program students in Language Learning Center. This research is classified as Classroom Action Research since the purpose of this research focuses on the improvement of the student's reading comprehension of narrative text by using comic strips. This process of procedures of this research is based on Kemmis and McTaggart, in McNiff and Whitehead (2002), and subsequent revisions depict a self-reflective spiral of planning, acting, observing, reflecting, and re-planning as the foundation for understanding how to take action to improve an educational situation. To collect the data, the researcher uses two techniques: observation and test. The data were analyzed with qualitative. The researcher determines whether this action research was successful based on the success criteria. The criteria are divided into two parts. First, the indicator of success is based on the teaching and learning process. If, during the teaching and learning process, the student's skill in reading comprehension of narrative text using comic strips improved, then this research is successful. Second, if the students 85% received a classical accomplishment score of 75 or higher. It implies that if the students receive a rating of 75 or more, they can be considered successful. This rating is based on the Language Learning Center's KKM standard.

Figure 1 Kemmis and McTaggart Cycle of Action Research

3. Research Findings

3.1. The First Cycle of Research

3.1.1. Planning

The time for research is allocated for six meetings. In the first meeting, the researcher explained reading strategies such as scanning, previewing, and predicting; vocabulary knowledge (guessing unknown vocabulary and guessing meaning from the context in a sentence), topic and topic of the paragraph; main idea; skimming, making Inference, and summarizing. The second meeting is designed to teach about narrative text language features such as action verbs, nouns, and adjectives. The third meeting is designed to give some material, such as explanations about the narrative text, the kinds of narrative text, the character of the narrative text, the generic structure of the narrative text, and the social function. In the fourth meeting, the researcher designed to review the material from the last meeting and gave the students a comic strip titled *The Legend of Lake Limboto*. The fifth meeting is designed to discuss the comic strip more deeply; the students must find the main idea of the text and determine the generic structure of the text, the social function, and the language feature of the text. The sixth meeting reviewed the material from the first to the sixth meeting. After that, the researcher gave the final test of the first cycle.

3.1.2. Observing

This step observed three points: the teacher's activity, students' activities, and reading comprehension results in the first cycle. The teacher's instrument of observation consisted of three main points that should be done such as pre, while, and post-activity. The collaborator used the teacher's observation sheet to ensure that the teaching-learning activities were suitable to the lesson plan that had been prepared previously. The result of the observation of the teacher's movement in the first cycle is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 The Result of The Observation of The Teacher's Activity in The First Cycle

No.	Indicators	Implementation		
		Good	Enough	Lack
I	Pre-activity			
1	Preparing students	√		
2	Check the readiness of students.	√		
3	Giving an apperception	√		
4	Telling the objective of teaching learning and topic	√		
II	While activities			
a	Mastery learning materials			
1	Showing mastery materials	√		
2	Convey the materials	√		
b	Learning techniques			
1	Implementing appropriate learning competencies	√		
2	Implementing coherent learning by the implementation steps of reading comprehension using comic strips	√		
3	Implement learning by the planned time allocation.		√	
4	Mastering class	√		
c	Utilization of learning resources			
1	Using the media effectively	√		
2	Produce an exciting message.		√	
d	Learning triggered the students' involvement.			
1	Foster the active participation of students in learning.		√	
2	Shows an open attitude towards students' response	√		
3	Cultivate joy and enthusiasm in learning.	√		
e	Rating			
1	Monitor the final assessment based on indicators for reading comprehension	√		
2	Conduct the final assessment based on indicators for reading comprehension.	√		
III	Post activity/Closing			
1	Reflection	√		
2	Telling activity for the next meeting	√		

Based on the activities of the teachers as described in Table 1, the observer assessed that the researcher had completed the indicators on the observation sheet during the teaching and learning process. However, several indicators did not perform to their full potential. First, implementing learning by the planned time allocation is not maximal. It is because many students still lack learning vocabulary in a comic strip with the title *The Legend of the Lake Limboto*. Thus, the researcher should guide them many times. The researcher cannot move to the following material. It is made the time

allocation is not maximal. Second, the aspect of learning triggered the students' involvement. The researcher found it hard to start the students to be involved in the class because, in the first and second meetings, the material focused on explaining reading comprehension and narrative text. Hence, the students are not too getting involved in that meeting. Third, the researcher is hard to foster the active participation of students in learning. Many students are insecure about answering questions because they fear being wrong. However, sometimes the researcher did not know whether the students understood the material. And then several students rarely attend the class, impacting their engagement. The next cycle should progress this condition because it affects the students' reading comprehension results.

The students' observational tools concentrated on group cooperation, personal dedication, and the use of comic strips during the reading comprehension process. The effectiveness of the student's performance and engagement during the reading comprehension exercise utilizing comic strips is evaluated using this observational tool. Table 2 displays the observation findings of students' first cycle activities.

Table 2 The Result of Observation of Students' Activities in The First Cycle

No.	Indicators	Implementation		
		Good	Enough	Lack
1	Students' cooperation in group			√
2	Individual commitment			√
3	Use comic strips	√		

The students' activities lacked individual and group dedication and teamwork. It is because when the researcher divided the students into several groups and gave them a worksheet, only two or three of them worked well, and some of them were quiet and just waited for others to finish the worksheet. It impacts their cooperation in the group. They are also lacking in individual commitment. For example, several of them rarely attend class. Thus, when they join a group, they find it hard to adjust to others.

Eventually, the indicators must be developed in the following cycle. The final point covered the first cycle's reading comprehension results for the students. The test results were used to evaluate the students' reading comprehension abilities. Table 3 displays the data analysis findings on the reading comprehension of narrative texts utilizing comic strips.

Table 3 The Classification of the Students in Reading Comprehension of Narrative Text in the First Cycle

No.	Classification	The amount of Value	Frequency	Percentage
1	Very good	86-100	4	19%
2	Good	68-85	4	19%
3	Enough	48-67	5	24%
4	Less	32-47	8	38%
Sum			21	100%

Table 3 demonstrates that four students (19%) are categorized as "very good," four students (19%) as "good," five students (24%) as "enough," and eight students (38%) are categorized as "less." The results showed that the action research should be continued in the following cycle because only eight students, or 38%, out of the twenty-one students were effective in learning or received a "very good" or "good" rating. While 13 students, or (62%) had difficulty learning. In other words, many pupils lacked the necessary reading comprehension skills for narrative texts that used comic strips. As a result, the researcher concluded that action research should be cycled repeatedly.

3.2. Reflection

Based on the data in the result of students in reading comprehension of narrative text using comic strips, the researcher obtained the Value of their ability or skill in reading comprehension using comic strips. If the students were classified into minimal-Value in KKM, only eight students could be stated as successful because the standard Value of KKM was 75.

In the reflection step, the researcher and collaborator discussed the result of students, the observation of the teacher and students' activities in teaching-learning, and the lesson plan. While observing students' activities and learning about narrative text-based comic strips, some students were confused about the meaning of the sentences in the comic. They could understand by seeing the picture and guessing the story's plot, but they did not understand the importance of the sentences. Their vocabulary is lacking, and they have never learned about narrative text. The researcher guided them to understand the story by explaining the story. It made the students pay attention to their tasks again.

In the beginning, when the researcher gave them the first comic strips with the title The Legend of The Lake Limboto, they were so excited because that is a legend from Gorontalo Province. But after they read the text, they are confused about the meaning of each word. Most of the students had some difficulties understanding the narrative text based on the comic strips well because they did not know the topic sentence of the story and so many words they did not know. Then, they did not see the type of narrative text, the generic structures of the story, language features, and the story's moral Value. Next, they did not understand what simple past tense is, primarily the use 2nd verb form, even though the simple past tense has been taught in their English class. The students also cannot differentiate personal pronouns, evidenced by the results of their exams which are, on average, wrong on the question about personal pronouns. The students also have difficulties pronouncing words because they are unfamiliar with certain words. Meanwhile, the students also have problems with reading comprehension tests because they are unfamiliar with the reading comprehension test, primarily narrative text.

Referring to the result of the first cycle, the researcher concluded that the cycle must be continued to the next step. Some problems must be solved in the next cycle.

3.3. The Second Cycle of Research

3.3.1. Revised planning

The standard of competence and basic competence was the same as the standard of competence in the first cycle, that is, analyzing the social function, text structure, and language features of several texts oral and written narratives by giving and asking for information related to the simple legend folk, according to the context of its use. While the basic competence that would be achieved is "Identifying the structure of the text and linguistic elements in spoken and narrative texts writing." Referring to the students' problems found in the first cycle, the researcher and collaborator formulated the objective of this learning. First, the students can identify the genetic structure of the narrative text, especially folklore, language features, and the story's moral Value.

3.3.2. Observing

This part discussed three points: the observation of the teacher's activity, the observation of students' activity, and the student's achievement in reading comprehension of narrative text. The result of the observation, teacher and students are based on analyzing the observation sheet used by the researcher and collaborator in the teaching-learning process. The student's achievement in reading comprehension of narrative text was viewed from the test result. First, the result of observing the teacher's activity can be seen in the following table.

Table 4 demonstrates how the researcher used the lesson plan's planned activities and the observation sheet's stated indicators. According to the collaborator who served as the observer, the researcher could complete all indications on the observation sheet. As a result, the researcher concluded that there had been an improvement in the teaching and learning process, which may have affected students' ability to read comprehension, mainly when narrative texts were used. The researcher would then present the findings of their second cycle of student activity observation. The table below shows it clearly.

Table 4 The Result of The Observation of The Teacher's Activity in The Second Cycle

No.	Indicators	Implementation		
		Good	Enough	Lack
1	Pre-activity			
1	Preparing students	√		
2	Check the readiness of students.	√		
3	Giving an apperception	√		
4	Telling the objective of teaching learning and topic	√		
II	While activities			
a	Mastery learning materials			
1	Showing mastery materials	√		
2	Convey the material	√		
b	Learning techniques			
1	Implement appropriate learning competencies.	√		
2	Implement coherent learning through the implementation steps of reading comprehension using comic strips.	√		
3	Implement learning by the planned time allocation.		√	
4	Mastering class	√		
c	Utilization of learning resources			
1	Using the media effectively	√		
2	Produce an exciting message.	√		
d	Learning triggered the students' involvement.			
1	Foster the active participation of students in learning.	√		
2	Shows an open attitude towards students' response	√		
3	Cultivate joy and enthusiasm in learning.	√		
e	Rating			
1	Monitor the final assessment based on indicators for reading comprehension		√	
2	Conduct the final assessment based on indicators for reading comprehension.		√	
III	Post activity/ Closing			
1	Reflection	√		
2	Telling activity for the next meeting	√		

Table 5 The Result of Observation of Students' Activities in The Second Cycle

No.	Indicators	Implementation		
		Good	Enough	Lack
1	Students' cooperation in group	√		
2	Individual commitment	√		
3	Use comic strips	√		

Based on the data in Table 5, the students have acted on all indicators so that the researcher could state that there was a significant improvement in students' activities in learning reading comprehension of narrative text using comic strips.

Table 6 The Classification of the Students in Reading Comprehension of Narrative Text in the Second Cycle

No.	Classification	The amount of Value	Frequency	Percentage
1	Very good	86-100	19	90%
2	Good	68-85	2	10%
3	Enough	48-67	-	-
4	Less	32-47	-	-
Sum			21	100%

Table 6 shows that nineteen students (90%) are classified well. They have values of more than 86. At the same time, two students (10%) are classified into good classification because they got values between 68 and 85. No one student is in enough and less category because they do not have values less than 48 and 32.

3.3.3. Reflection

The student's reading comprehension skills have significantly improved, as shown by analyzing the achievement statistics from the first and second cycles. Four students (19%) from the first cycle were given the term "good classification," while two students from the second cycle were given the same label. In contrast, four students from the first cycle and nineteen from the second cycle were labelled "very good classifications." According to the indications of success, it can be determined that the activities in the second cycle were successful if the students had values of 75 or more, and 100 % of the students had values of 75 or more classically. It indicates that since the research's goal has been met, the activities in the following cycle should not continue.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Students' Skill in Reading Comprehension of Narrative Text by Using Comic Strips

The student's skill in reading comprehension is viewed from the aspect of reading comprehension. The elements of reading comprehension include main idea (topic), expression/idioms/phrases in context, Inference (implied detail), grammatical feature, detail (scanning for expressly stated detail), excluding fact not written (unstated detail), supporting the idea, and vocabulary in context. These aspects are based on Brown (2003). In providing the students' results in reading comprehension on every cycle, the researcher used the minimal standard criterion (KKM) 75.

The researcher discovered that the student's reading comprehension in the first cycle was low. The students were taught the components of reading comprehension, such as identifying the main idea, identifying supporting details, understanding vocabulary, identifying Inference, and making inferences, before the researcher evaluated them on reading comprehension of narrative text using comic strips. Unfortunately, it was discovered that the student's reading comprehension abilities were lacking after examining their test results.

The results of the student's reading comprehension tests show they had difficulty understanding the narrative text. Finding the textbooks throughout there is the first challenge. The story's topic was complex for the students to identify, and they were not paying attention to it. The researcher instructed the students to identify the subject of the comic strip's narrative to resolve this issue.

The researcher discovered that the students' issue was that they could not articulate their ideas using the standard format of narrative texts. To solve this issue, the researcher talked with the students about the general narrative format seen in comic strips. Furthermore, the researcher provided them with a comic book that described a generic structure. It is to make it simpler for the students to comprehend the text's general structure.

In expression/idioms/phrases in context, the researcher found the students did not familiar with idioms and expressions in the text. Most of them translated it word by word and did not understand the implied meaning of the text. To solve this problem, the researcher gives the students more idioms, especially in the text, and the researcher also tells the story with the expression of the story. It is to make the students understand the story.

In Inference or implied detail, the researcher found that the students did not know the meaning of the text. However, they have difficulties making inferences about the text. To overcome these problems, the researcher discussed the story with the students and gave them exercises to practice their knowledge about the implied meaning of the text. The students also have difficulties determining the writer's purpose and message of the text. To solve this problem, the researcher guides them to find the story's moral Value and concludes what lessons can be learned from it.

The researcher observed the students' difficulties with the simple past in terms of grammar. The researcher gave them a task and an explanation of the simple past to help them comprehend its application. The researcher gave them a comic describing language features, one of which is a simple past tense used in narrative text. The researcher also explains the use of simple past tense in narrative text. It is essential because simple past tense is a dominant structure used in narrative text.

In detail (scanning for expressly stated detail), the researcher found the students are easier to determine the detailed information of the text. Sometimes, they also find checking for expressly stated details difficult because they are unfamiliar with several words. To solve this problem, the researcher discussed with the students about the comic strips. She also asked them for some detailed information about the text. It is to practice their understanding of the text. In unstated detail (excluding facts not written), the researcher found that the students found it challenging to determine the unstated detail of the text or facts not written on it. It is because they translated the text word by word. Hence, they find it difficult to understand the implied meaning of the text. To overcome this problem, the researcher gave them worksheets to practice their reading skill and determine the unstated detail of the text.

In supporting the idea, the researcher found that the students found it challenging to differentiate the text's central argument and supporting statement. To solve this problem, the researcher explained more to the students about the main idea (topic), supporting idea, and how to determine the main idea and supporting idea. In vocabulary in context, the researcher found that is a central problem for the students. It is because mastering vocabulary is a crucial aspect of comprehending reading. If they have a complex vocabulary, they will find it difficult to determine the main idea, supporting idea, text detail, unstated detail, and Inference of the text. To overcome this problem, the researcher gave the students a game about vocabulary to quickly remember the text's vocabulary.

Finally, in the second cycle, the students' narrative text was suitable for reading comprehension. There is the main idea (topic), expression/idioms/phrases in context, Inference, grammatical feature, detail (scanning for expressly stated detail), excluding fact not written (unstated detail), supporting the idea, and vocabulary in context. Most of them got a good score, and several got a perfect score. It shows that the student's skills in reading comprehension increased significantly.

4.2. The Use of Comic Strips Can Improve Students' Reading Comprehension of Narrative Text

Based on the result of the research findings, the first and second cycle shows that there is a significant improvement in students' skill in reading comprehension of narrative text in class English for Teens Program in the Language Learning Center. The improvement could be known by the increasing number of students who got standard values or KKM. In the first cycle, four students, 19%, could reach the standard of Value based on KKM. But, in the second cycle, after the researcher revised the planning, nineteen students or 100%, could achieve the standard of Value based on KKM.

By analyzing the result of students' reading comprehension achievement in the first cycle, eight aspects of reading comprehension must be repaired. There are main ideas, expression/idioms/phrases in context, Inference, grammatical feature, detail (scanning for expressly stated detail), supporting ideas, and vocabulary in context. These aspects are based on Brown (2003).

The researcher found this evidence when she analyzed the students' reading skills in the reading comprehension rubric. The percentage of students reading skills was 38% classically successful, and 62% were unsuccessful. It means that most students did not achieve the Value of 75 or more as the minimum value criteria. This condition indicated that the student's reading comprehension of narrative text was not an as easy task for the students. They said many words in the text that they did not understand, so they had difficulty interpreting the sentences and understanding the story's contents.

By revising the teaching-learning process in the second cycle, the researcher found that the student's skill in reading comprehension could be improved. In the second cycle, the researcher focused on the student's difficulties with vocabulary. The result of the student's achievement in the second cycle shows that there is a significant improvement in the student's skills in reading comprehension of narrative text. The percentage of students' achievement was 90%, who could reach a value more than 86, and 10% are classified into good classification because they got values between 68 and 86. In other words, all students could achieve the standard of Value based on KKM.

Mastering vocabulary is a critical factor in the success of teaching-learning in reading comprehension of narrative material utilizing comic strips. Therefore, the students can understand the text more easily. Mc supports it. Vicker (2014) stated that comic strips would help students better understand the content. The process of increasing or extending comprehension in terms of understanding the text will occur due to seeing the picture and connecting it to the text. The researcher concludes that comic strips could improve students' reading comprehension of narrative material by studying and utilizing their experiences to teach reading comprehension.

The Limitation of Research

The action research has various limitations, including the following: first, comic strips are an alternate media in the teaching-learning process. It is used to teach reading comprehension and is intended to improve students' ability to comprehend narrative text comprehension. However, this action research is limited in improving students' reading comprehension of narrative content. The action did not produce narrative items but focused on examining students' reading skills from the reading comprehension perspective. Second, this action study was conducted in the English for Teens Program in the Language Learning Center to improve student's reading comprehension of narrative text using comic strips.

5. Conclusion

The researcher concludes that employing comic strips can help students become more adept at reading narrative texts after carefully examining how this action research was carried out and how the results were discussed. The results of the student's performance in reading comprehension of narrative material utilizing comic strips in the first cycle were unsatisfactory. Only 19% of the students met the bare minimum standard Value (KKM) in the first cycle. In the second cycle, the researcher changed the teaching and learning process, such as giving the students worksheets, giving games to improve their vocabulary, providing several quizzes, and designing comic strips with colourful signs. Therefore, the students can identify the generic structure of the text more easily. Eventually, the student's reading comprehension skills in narrative text using comic strips improves. In the second cycle, 100% of students reached the minimum standard Value (KKM). The ability of the students to understand narrative material utilizing comic strips could be improved when the teaching and learning process has been revised. The students' reading skills dramatically improved. The study's findings showed that employing comic strips as a teaching tool for reading comprehension can help students become more adept at understanding the narrative text.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Aisy, R. A., Hatip, M., & Nuraini, K.(2019). The Effect of Using Comic Strips on Reading Comprehension Achievement. Repository Universitas Muhammadiyah Jember.p-4. <http://repository.unmuhjember.ac.id/6738/1/TABLE%20OF%20CONTENT%20AND%20LIST%20%20OF%20APPENDICES.pdf>
- [2] Amrizal, A., & Hamdani, Z. (2017). The Effect of a Cooperative Script in Enhancing the Students' Narrative Writing. *Jurnal Smart*, 3(2), 84–89. <https://doi.org/10.26638/465.203x>
- [3] Asrori, & Rusman. (2020). *Classroom action reserach pengembangan kompetensi guru*. Purwokerto: Pena Persada.
- [4] Brown, Douglass (2003). *Language Assessment Principles and Classroom Practices*. San Fransisco: Longman.
- [5] Hasan, M. M. D. H. K. T. (2021). *Media Pembelajaran*. In Tahta Media Group (Issue Mei).
- [6] Kemmis, S., McTaggart, R., & Nixon, R. (2014). The action research planner: Doing critical participatory action research. In *The Action Research Planner: Doing Critical Participatory Action Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-4560-67-2>
- [7] McCloud, S. (2006). *Making Comics Storytelling Secrets of Comics, Manga, and Graphic Novels*. Harper Collins Publishers. New York. p-2.
- [8] McKay, S L. (2006). *Researching Second Language Classroom*. London: Lawrence Erlbaun Associates, Publishers
- [9] McNiff, J., & Whitehead, J. (2002). *Action Research Principles and Practices Second Edition*. London: Taylor & Francis e-Library
- [10] Rokhayani, A., Ririn, A., & Utari, P. (2014). The Use of Comic Strips As an English Teaching Media for Junior High School Students. *LANGUAGE CIRCLE Journal of Language and Literature*, VIII(2), 143.
- [11] Yunus, M. M., Salehi, H., & Embi, M. A. (2012). Effects of using digital comics to improve ESL writing. *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, 4(18), 3462–3469.